

2024 NASA Software Workshop STI Services, STRIVES, and Software

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Scientific and Technical Information
Information, Data, & Analytics Services (IDAS)
Office of the Chief Information Officer

STI Compliance and Distribution Services

NASA STI Services

The Agency-wide [STI Compliance and Distribution Services](#) collects, organizes, manages, disseminates, and provides for long-term retention of NASA's STI.

What is STI?

NASA STI is defined as the results (facts, analyses, and conclusions) of basic and applied scientific, technical, and related engineering research and development. STI also includes management, industrial, and economic information relevant to this research.

STRIVES Process

NASA has a responsibility to ensure the scientific and technical information (STI) it releases is technically accurate, is appropriately marked for any restrictions, and does not violate any export control and intellectual property federal laws and statutes.

The NASA Scientific and Technical Information (STI) Discovery System ([STRIVES](#)) process is the dissemination or release approval process by which NASA also determines which restrictions, if any, need to be placed on a document.

Benefits of the STI STRIVES Process:

- Determines how a document may be released or restricted
- Provides a review of export-controlled content and intellectual property concerns
- Increases public access to NASA's scientific publications and digital scientific data

Approval is crucial to ensuring:

- Technical accuracy and professional quality
- That management has approved the document for release
- That restricted information is not released publicly

When is a STRIVES review required?

A review is done prior to releasing STI internally where foreign nationals may be present or disseminating externally to a public/non-NASA audience.

Who reviews the STI?

The Agency requires a least four different STRIVES approvers to review and clear STI for release.

The STRIVES submission routes to the following approvers:

- ✓ Management Approver (*Acceptability for release*)
- ✓ Center STI Staff (*Quality review*)
- ✓ Center Patent Counsel Office (*Copyright, inventions, patents, and third-party content guidance*)
- ✓ Center Export Control Office (*EAR and ITAR*)

Does the STRIVES review requirement apply to all authors?

Civil servants and contractors whose contracts specify the review requirement are required to put their STI through the STRIVES review. Grantee authors do not have the review requirement unless specifically directed by NASA.

Public Access

All NASA-funded researchers (both civil servant and non-civil servant) are required to ensure that copies of NASA-funded peer-reviewed publications are made available in NASA's designated public access repository, [PubSpace](#).

Software and Publications

NPR 2210.1E, Release of NASA Software

Section P.2 Applicability, Section (3) g.

This NPR does not apply to Scientific Research Demonstration Software (as defined in Appendix A) that is developed and used for the purpose of supporting a scientific publication. Such publication-related software may be released with the scientific publication, but, as part of the **NPR 2200.2, Requirements for Documentation, Approval and Dissemination of Scientific and Technical Information**, review process for dissemination of scientific and technical information, the author/management is responsible to confirm that the related software meets the requirements set forth in the definition of **Scientific Research Demonstration Software**. The ability to distribute such software under NPR 2200.2 does not also permit the inclusion or release of any underlying software that may be related to the subject of the scientific publication, which would still need to be reported and released under NPR 2210.

Appendix A: Definition of Scientific Research Demonstration Software

Scientific Research Demonstration Software - Software written to perform minor analyses of scientific concepts or experimental data that would be classified as Class E Software under NPR 7150.2. Such software is developed and used by NASA for the purpose of supporting the analysis presented within a scientific publication and has no other current NASA mission purpose at the time of publication. While the Authors/Innovators of such software are U.S. Government civil servants, such software may call third-party software scripts and libraries, but only where such scripts and libraries are provided under a permissive license that does not prohibit or qualify NASA's use and release. Such software may not incorporate any third-party software. (NPR 2210.1E, Release of NASA Software, NPR 2210.1E – Appendix A, https://nodis3.gsfc.nasa.gov/npg_img/N_PR_2210_001E_/N_PR_2210_001E_.pdf)

Scientific Research Demonstration Software and STRIVES

- Scientific Research Demonstration Software
 - Software authored by civil servants only
 - No use of third-party licenses unless permissions granted
 - Software written to perform minor analyses of scientific concepts or experimental data that would be classified as Class E Software under NPR 7150.2.
 - Not reviewed via the Software Release Process, NPR 2210.1
- **What's not Scientific Research Demonstration Software**
 - Software classified as Class A, B, C, D, or F via the NPR 7150.2 2 NASA Software Engineering Requirements classifications.
 - Software developed for the operations of a mission.
 - Software that would be restricted from release by ITAR, export control, or other security restrictions.
 - Level 0 to Level 1 data processing pipelines or later stage data processing pipelines developed by the mission team.
 - Simulation software for a mission developed by the mission team.
 - Software developed for the archiving and distribution of NASA data.
 - Commercial software
 - Reviewed via the Software Release Process, NPR 2210.1
- STRIVES is not currently designed to handle the inclusion of Scientific Research Demonstration Software as supplementary information with a publication. This will require system engineering changes and defining the process. Currently, STRIVES can review publications, but we cannot software files until all the system and process modifications are made.

STI Information

- Main STI SharePoint site: [STI Compliance and Distribution Services](#)
- STI Handbook: <https://nasa.sharepoint.com/sites/NASASTIProgram/SitePages/STI-Policy-&-Guidance.aspx>
- Join STI User Group: [STRIVES and STI Repository \(NTRS\) User Group](#)
- Become member of the STI Communications Distribution List: [STI Communications Distribution List](#)

STRIVES and NTRS

- STRIVES: <https://strives.nasa.gov>
- STRIVES Resources: <https://nasa.sharepoint.com/sites/NASASTIProgram/SitePages/STRIVES.aspx>
- STI Repository (NTRS): <https://ntrs.nasa.gov>

Policies:

- NPD 2200.1: [Management of NASA Scientific and Technical Information](#)
- NPR 2200.2: [Requirements for Documentation, Approval and Dissemination of Scientific and Technical Information](#)
- NPR 2210.1E, [Release of NASA Software](#)
- NPD 2230.1, [Research Data and Publication Access](#)